

Recent Archaeological Discoveries in Villupuram District, TamilNadu, India

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ABSTRACT

Archaeology and the cultural heritage of our forefathers were unique and outstanding. As per the Archaeological sources, Villupuram district is considered to be an ancient place. This recent archaeological discoveries in Villupuram district is very much essential for the reconstruction and restructuring of the history of Villupuram district. This research aptly discusses the great phenomenon of recent archaeological discoveries made by the exploration of new findings by the present research scholar. The archaeological vestiges in the form of pre-historic tools of Paleolithic, Mesolithic, Neolithic ages besides the occurrence of rock paintings, Iron Age burials and habitation sites exemplify the human activity of the contemporary period. With this gamut of archaeological finds of the district, one can visualize the social scenario that Villupuram passed through the ages and the same could be the pride of the current as well as the future generation in creating an eco-friendly environ promoting tourism, culture, and tradition. Villupuram district is not only special on the Archaeological basis. From this archaeological discoveries research, one fact is quite obvious that the District of Villupuram has always played a significant role in the annals of Tamilnadu from the days immemorial.

Key Words: Villupuram District, Iron Age, Archaeology, tradition, Pallava

Introduction

The history of India is replete with significant events, which took place in different regions from time immemorial. Each region and sub-region has played a remarkable role, which had not been understood adequately by the posterity. Archaeology and the cultural heritage of our forefathers were unique and outstanding. Many scholars of the recent years have understood the importance of Archaeological sources and have endeavored to bring to light many of these aspects which are higher and have not seen the light of the day. As per the Archaeological sources, Villupuram district is considered to be an ancient place. Also this district as revealed by the archaeology is highly appreciable. This recent archaeological discoveries in Villupuram district is very much essential for the reconstruction and restructuring of the history of Villupuram district. This research aptly discusses the great phenomenon of recent archaeological discoveries made by the exploration of new findings by the present research scholar.

Recent Archaeological Discoveries In Villupuram District

The Archaeological significance of the Villupuram District was identified through surface surveys and salvage exploration, which led researchers to put forward the hypothesis, that villupuram District would have been in the ancient past and anterior to the Indus vally civilization. The following Archaeological Sites are new discoveries in Villupuram District.

Devadanampettai (Dolmens and Rock Arts Paintings)

Many archaeological evidences were found in Devadanapettai hills, near Gingee which belongs to the same taluk of Villupuram district. In this hill numerous Dolmens are noticed. A lot of rock art paintings were also found inside the large cave located on the north side of this hill.¹ These rock art paintings and Dolmens are seen in rich natural colours at three places.

In the first place there are two human tattoos including a woman and a man's shapes. In the second place one could find a woman's tattoo without a head. A human tattoo which is found in the third place seems to look like a man is worshipping the god with his two hands.² Hence, it is surmised that the human race stayed here and worshipped the god.

Varikal (Jain beds and Sangam age bricks)

Ancient Jain monks had preferably chosen secluded caves and caverns as their shelters for privacy to perform austere practices meant for the spiritual growth. This is mainly to avoid the

mundane environ of worldly pleasures and to refrain from such desires for the upliftment of the soul.³ Moreover the isolated locations of shelters, away from the human habitation area really encouraged their religions practice. Initially they stayed in rough rocky surfaces. Later such resting places were smoothed and shaped as rock beds containing pillow like elevated portions serving as resting beds. The Jain monks created rock beds in Taminadu right from 3rd century BC. Such Jain rock beds discovered at Varikal in Gingee Taluk also yielded Sangam age size bricks forming part of the existing structure.⁴ It deserves much attention as it has great archaeological potentialities.

Kilsevir (Durga Idol)

The exploration of a research scholar at Kilsevir of Tindivanam taluk brought out the exposure of a Pallava style Durga from a pond.⁵ This Durga is unique with a deer as its vahana while a later period sculpture of this deity possesses a lion as her vahana. During the Sangam age Durga is variously known as Kortravai, Thai kalai pavai and so on. This many armed image of measurement 142 cms height, 108 cms breadth, stands in samabanga posture over a the mahisha (buffalo demon) head.⁶ On stylistic grounds this sculpture belongs to the Pallava period of execution.⁷ There is also a Jyesta image near the lake of the village.

Ayanampalayam (Jyestadevi and Thirmal Idol)

Ayanampalayam is adjoining to Villupuram Town where a few more Sculpture were discovered from this area particularly Jyestadevi was discovered.⁸ In fact Jyestadevi was under worship till the 10th century A.D. but lost her importance due to the misconception of treating her as bestower of evils and bad qualities. Generally such sculpture exists on the northwestern corner of the Siva temple of the villages adjacent to a pond, lake, river bunds. This sculpture at Ayanampalaiyam measures 78cm height, 58 cms breadth.⁹ At the lower right side is depicted an individual in salutation posture and on the left side is shown a servant maid with a bowl on her head. Apart from this Jeshta sculpture, there is also a Vishnu image in standing posture with 4 arms.¹⁰ This sculpture belongs to the 7th century A.D. Pallava art tradition.¹¹ From these sculptures found in Ayanampalayam, it is inferred that the people of that contemporary period worshipped both Jeshtadevi as well as Vishnu.

Kappiyampuliyur (Murugan Idol)

The Murugan Idol is found at the centre of the Siva temple tank of the village located in Vikravandi taluk enroute Villupuram-Kumbakonam highway.¹³ This image is taken for lord Indira by the local people.¹⁴ But this stone slab has relief sculpture measuring 120cms high and 59 cms breadth. It is actually the form of Lord Muruga seated on an elephant, holding a lotus bud in his right arm and

possessing an ankusa down wards in the left hand.¹⁵ His head dress consists of three concentric circled Karanda makuda with a bloomed lotus beautifully decorating by the crown.¹⁶ He wears keyura and kankanas on his hands. The elephant in the walking mood is represented with its trunk turned and found on the left, stretched out ear lobes, blunt tusks with rings. It becomes the vehicle of Lord Muruga being flanked on either side by chamaradar is (fannig people). On the right shoulder top is shown an umbrella, although Lord Muruga's vahana is peacock. It is very well confirmed by the reference in Thirumurugatrupadai, Paripadal of Sangam classics. Kannanur Balasubramaniya temple of early Chola time and the Swamimalai temple (one of the Arupadai vidu of Lord Muruga) also contain elephant as vahana.¹⁷ Apart from this there is another sculpture of Lord Muruga found seated on an elephant at Anankur near Kappiyampuliyur with 4 arms holding sakti, aksamala, which also deserves special mention. It was located and identified earlier by the Archaeologists of the State Government Department.¹⁸ On execution, this sculptural representation is far more eloquent, excellent with much beauty, aesthetic qualities and majesty. The head dress and the elephant vehicle of the lord made the common folk of the village to call him lord Indira. The style of the image recalls the late Pallava phase of sculptural art of the 9th century A.D.

Kanjiur (Pallava Era Stone)

The present research scholar's team were conducting research at Kanjiur mountain range. They unearthed the ancient medicine grinding stone which was sculpted by a Pallava army commander 'Achiliyan' for medicinal purposes.¹⁹ After analysing the inscriptions embossed in it, the archaeologists ascertained that this grinding stone was sculpted by the Pallava army chief and had contributed to Jains who were doing medical and educational service to the villagers during the Pallava era.²⁰

Sevalapurai (Inscriptions of Pandya and Sambuvaraya periods)

A team of research scholars under the present research found two inscriptions at Agatheeswarar temple at Sevalapurai near Gingee in Villupuram district, which belongs to the Pandya and Sambuvaraya periods.²¹ The first inscription belongs to 1312 AD the during the rule of Jadavarma Sundarapandian. The village of Sevalapurai was once called Jayakonda Chozhamandalathu Singapuranaatu Sevalapuraiyur. The inscription provides information about various tax collections and country divisions. It also says that after the Chozha rule, Pandya rule came to stay in the region. This temple was once called Agathesuramudiya Naayanar temple and land donations for the temple are also mentioned.²² In the farmland on the northern side of the temple, the second inscription was found. This belongs to Rasanarayanan Thirumallinathan Sambuvaraya period in 1356 AD. The inscription

mentions AnjinanPugalidam, a refuge camp for people, who escaped from war, in the name of Sonadu Kondan Thiruveedhi. Sonadu Kondan means a person who won the Chozha dynasty.²³ These two inscriptions were helpful in tracing the History of the Village.

Sevalapurai (Durga Idol)

In Sevalapurai Village, a new discovery of Durag Sculpture was made. This shows that the idol belongs to the starting period of Pallavas.²⁴ In Tamil Nadu, this kind of idol was earlier found in some places. After checking the inscription, we confirmed that this is the oldest Durga idol of this type found in Tamil Nadu. The idol has been carved out on a slab kind of stone, which is 165 cm in height and 63 cm in breadth. The Goddess is seen standing on the head of Mageesha and behind her is a deer. The Goddess has eight hands carrying a chakra, sword, shield, conch and bow. She also has two hands on her hip.

"Durga alias Kottravai is also called as En Tholi, means eight shoulders. 'Karanda Magudam' is seen on her head, but the jewels on her neck could not be identified clearly. In the bottom is a devotee praying to her. On her left is a devotee in standing position. We guess the face of Durga was modified during a later period.²⁵ The Research team was able to read two lines in Vattezhuthu inscription- 'Venkundra Kottathu' (N)npettu (Ravaro) Selvithare. "This shows Nanpedu is a village in Venkundram region, and a person from there, carved this idol. As the inscription was damaged a little, the name of the sculptor couldn't be deciphered.

S.Rajagopal, a senior inscription researcher, found in Arachalur, Poolankuruchi and Irulapatti, the starting stage of Vattezhuthu inscription. The inscription here looks similar. So, we can say that this inscription belongs to sixth century, the starting of Pallava era. Rajagopal added that this was before Pallava king Magendravarman, and before he made Kudaivarai temples.

Conclusion

The longest period of mankind is popularly termed as the pre-historic age and to trace its history, sources like literature, inscriptions and coins are of only to a certain extent. The archaeological vestiges in the form of pre-historic tools of Paleolithic, Mesolithic, Neolithic ages besides the occurrence of rock paintings, iron age burials and habitation sites exemplify the human activity of the contemporary period.

Then the vestiges of Sangam age really portrays their high standard of living from hunter gatherers to settlers of statesmanship. It was during the Pallava times the marvels of art and

architecture came into being to educate the society of the various forms of Hindu, Jain gods, goddesses and thereby to refine their social behavior. With this gamut of archaeological finds of the district, one can visualize the social scenario that Villupuram passed through the ages and the same could be the pride of the current as well as the future generation in creating an eco-friendly environ promoting tourism, culture, and tradition.

Villupuram district is not only special on the Archaeological basis. It is a cultural link between south and north Tamilnadu. So, it reflects the full cultural view of Tamilnadu. In a nutshell, Villupuram district possesses a concrete evidence of its pre-historic, proto-historic, early historic and historic phase of cultures reflecting the social, economical, religious and political conditions of the respective periods. From this archaeological discoveries research, one fact is quite obvious that the District of Villupuram has always played a significant role in the annals of Tamilnadu from the days immemorial.

The above findings have been made through the authentic and genuine research undertaken by the present researcher purely by himself. Individual it is a matter of pride and joy for the present researcher to unveil an unknown facet of Villupuram District through his own research.

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